

The Effects of Fermented Plant Juice (FPJ) on the Growth of Peanut Crop

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Abstract

Based on the results of the study there was a significant difference on height of peanut plant were measured from the ground level up to the tip of the main shoot at every 10 days after applying the treatments, and on the average number of leaves of peanut crop. Statistical analysis shows the significant difference of Plot A and Plot B on the responses of peanut crop that received FPJ treatments to peanut that do not received treatment. Hence, it is recommended the use of fermented plant juice (FPJ) on peanut crop as it helps increases its growth performance of peanut crop specifically the plant height and number of leaves. Moreover, FPJ helps in improving the health of peanut plants and help them grow vigorously.

Introduction

Peanut (*Arachis hypogaea*) are a legume that originated in South America. They go by a variety of names, such as groundnuts, earthnuts, and goobers. Despite their name, peanuts are unrelated to tree nuts. As a legume, they are related to beans, lentils, and soy. It is widely grown in the tropics and subtropics, important to both small and large commercial producers. It is classified as both a grain legume, and an oil crop due to its high oil content. Peanuts are consumed all over the world in a wide variety of forms, most of which are traditional cuisine (Perea-Moreno, Miguel-Ángel, Manzano-Agugliaro, Francisco, Hernández- Escobedo, Quetzalcoatl, Perea, Alberto.2018. *Peanut Shell for Energy: Properties and Its Potential to Respect the Environment*. 10. 10.3390/su1009325).

Peanut farming in the Philippines is a thriving and profitable agricultural business. Before planting, farmers consider the seeds, soil, and water. The top producing region of peanuts in the Philippines is Luzon that has an 80% of total peanut production. Globally, peanut is the 13th most important food crop and the annual world production of shelled peanut in 2016 was 44 million tons (*Perea-Moreno, Miguel-Ángel, Manzano-Agugliaro, Francisco, Hernández- Escobedo, Quetzalcoatl, Perea, Alberto.2018. Peanut Shell for Energy: Properties and Its Potential to Respect the Environment. 10. 10.3390/su1009325*).

Fermented plant Juice (FPJ) is a fermented extract of a plant's sap and chlorophyll's. It is a rich enzyme solution full of microorganisms such as lactic acid bacteria and yeast that invigorates plants and animals. FPJ is used for crop treatments through drenching the soil with the solution or directly spraying it onto fruits and flowers. FPJ as soil fertilizer allows plants to improve their health and helps them grow vigorously. FPJ consist of different types of plants that are allowed to ferment for approximately 7 days with the help of molasses or brown sugar (*Ellaine Kryss Hubilla.2020. Fermented Plant Juice (FPJ) can spur plant growth.Agriculture Magazine*).

The benefits of Fermented Plant (FPJ) to peanut crop is it provides more nitrogen, that is why it is easy for peanut crop to photosynthesize. Fermented Plant Juice has phosphorus, potassium, calcium, and magnesium. Phosphorus is needed for good root development, while potassium is needed for flower and fruits setting, and the calcium strengthens the cell walls of a plant making it sturdy, and prevents fruits and flowers from falling off the plant. Also, magnesium helps keep the foliage green, helps in the photosynthetic process, and increased the nutrient absorption of the plant (*Sherwin Anthony.2023. The benefits of using fermented plant juice and how to make it. Gardenislife*). Hence, this study was conducted in order to determine the effect of FPJ on peanut crop, and to evaluate and compare the growth performance of peanut crop to treatments with no FPJ application.

Methodology

The materials and equipment that were used in this study were processed FPJ, shovel, spade, and hand trowel. The peanut crop that were used in the experimental plots is NSIC Pn19 peanut variety.

The research study used a quantitative methods. The researcher used two experimental plots for the comparison of the treatment application. Plot A experimental field were planted with NSIC Pn19 peanut variety and applied with Fermented Plant Juice (FPJ), while Plot B experimental field were planted with NSIC Pn19 peanut variety and with no FPJ application. The difference between each plot were determined and evaluated by the comparison of Plot A and Plot B growth performance in term of plant height and number of leaves.

The total plot size of both experimental field was 3 meters in width and 34 meters in length, including the 0.5 meter space in the center that separates the two plots. The treatments used in the study were: Treatment A, with FPJ application and Treatment B, without FPJ application.

Land Preparation

The experimental area were prepared prior to plating. It was plowed twice and harrowed to allow organic matter to decompose, pulverize the soil, destroy the weeds using the hand trowel, to attain a good seed emergence.

Planting

The peanut seeds were planted to both experimental field, Plot A, and Plot B. Each plot has 125 holes and each holes consisted of 2 peanut seeds. Plant spacing were observed at 60 cm with row spacing og 63 cm.

Watering and Weeding Management

Watering was done as soon as the soil are dry by using water sprayer. The soil is not waterlogged and with just enough watering keeps the soil moist. Weeding was done as soon as the weeds emerged. This was done through hand pulling and uprooting using hand trowel. Weeding was done twice a week to eliminate competition for light, water, and nutrients in the soil.

Treatment Application

The treatments were prepared following the procedure. After the treatments were prepared the 8 ml fermented plant juice (FPJ) is mixed with 1 gallon of water, shake it well and then it is ready to spray as foliar fertilizer on the peanut crop. The FPJ were sprayed onto the plants and into the soil and were applied to Plot A at every 10 days.

Harvesting

Harvesting of peanut crop was done at 80 - 100 days after sowing, when the crop reach its maturity state. The nuts were brown on the outside, firm and dry. It is best to dig out the peanut crop carefully in order to avoid breaking off of nuts and damage.

Data gathered and Statistical analysis

Plant height was gathered and measured from the ground level up to the tip of the main shoot at every 10 days after application of treatments, while the number of leaves was gathered by counting the leaves manually at every 10 days after the application of treatments. In analyzing the data t-test was used to determine the growth performance of the peanut crop in plot A (*with FPJ application*), and Plot B (*without FPJ application*) . The t-test was used to compare the means of the two groups, as it was used to test the hypothesis in determining whether the process

or treatment actually has an effect on the population of interest or whether the two groups are different from one another.

Summary of Findings and Conclusion

Based on the data gathered and statistical analysis on the growth performance of peanut crop on Plot A and Plot B, it was observed that the plant height of peanut crop shows that there was a significant difference on the responses of peanut crop on Plot A (*with FPJ application*) as compared to Plot B (*without FPJ application*). As shown in table 1, Plot A has an average plant height of 15.74 cm, 21.36 cm, and 24.46 cm while Plot B has an average of 13.98 cm, 16.46 cm, and 19.18 cm, respectively.

Table 1. Average Plant Height (cm) of peanut crop at 10, 20, 30 DAP

PLOT	Days After Planting (DAP)		
	10	20	30
A (with FPJ application)	15.74	21.36	24.46
B (without FPJ application)	13.98	16.46	19.18

Based on the data gathered and statistical analysis on the growth performance of peanut crop on Plot A and Plot B, it was observed that the number of leaves of peanut crop shows that there was a significant difference between treatment means. As shown in table 2, Plot A (*with FPJ application*) produced a higher number of leaves with an average of 44.38, 223.68, and 366.66, respectively as compared to Plot B (*without FPJ application*) with an average of 34.92, 155.40, and 268.68, respectively.

Table 2. Average Number of Leaves (cm) of peanut crop at 10, 20, 30 DAP

PLOT	Days After Planting (DAP)		
	10	20	30
A (with FPJ application)	44.38	223.68	366.66
B (without FPJ application)	34.92	155.40	268.68

The application of fermented plant juice (FPJ) on peanut crop shows a significant effect on the growth performance of the crop. Based on the summary of findings of this study it was observed and statistically analyzed that Plot A (*with FPJ application*) shows significant difference on plant height and the number of leaves of the peanut crop as its response to FPJ application on the crop. Hence, it is recommended the use of fermented plant juice (FPJ) on peanut crop as it helps increase its growth performance of peanut crop specifically the plant height and number of leaves. Moreover, FPJ helps in improving the health of peanut plants and help them grow vigorously making it more sustainable, environmentally friendly and cost-effective to crop farmers especially in the rural areas.

References

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